

General Article**Theoretical and practical concepts of Psychiatric Network Neuroscience**

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Abstract (414 words)

Network science has developed considerably over the last three decades through the study of complex natural and artificial systems. Several concepts from this field have subsequently been adopted in neuroscience for the study of brain function and, specifically, in psychiatry for research on the pathophysiology of psychiatric disorders and for the development of clinically meaningful diagnostic and therapeutic applications. The aim of the present article is: i) to present both the fundamental theoretical assumptions required for the classical node-centric network description of complex systems and ii) the practical steps needed for its application in psychiatric research and its successful implementation in treatment-oriented research.^{1,2,3}

In the first, theoretical part of the article, strict technical definitions for systems, graphs, and networks are introduced, using the mesolimbic reward system as a physical and neurobiological example. Subsequently, the concept of complex systems and their essential dual characteristic properties of heterogeneity and emergence are analyzed. The analysis includes the small-world phenomenon as a main element of the organization of the human connectome and as an essential underpinning of segregation and integration of brain function.

In the second, application-oriented part of the article, the basic steps for the identification of a network in the human brain are presented, using the node-centric model of network theory. At the core of the process is the importance of the psychiatric research question as a driver for the selection of measured quantities, recording and measurement methods, node and edge definitions, thresholding strategy, preprocessing methods, and software for recorded signal analysis. Finally, the creation of an adjacency matrix from thresholded data is described as the basis of network analysis. The extraction of the most commonly used network metrics following the creation of an adjacency matrix is presented, and their definitions are both explained and described schematically. Practical applications of network metrics in psychiatric research, diagnostic research, and the development of treatment methods are presented, using a hypothetical experiment in the mesolimbic reward system as an example.

The article is accompanied by an online Supplement, where: i) a short history of network neuroscience in the Greek research context is presented; ii) a pipeline, the General Protocol for Network Identification, Extraction, and Analysis, is described; iii) a schematic representation of the problem of metrics interpretation in neuroscience is provided; iv) an extended reference table with the limitations of network neuroscience methods, their solutions, and specific bibliographic references is presented; and v) advanced network-based descriptions of complex systems, such as higher-order network structures or edge-centric models⁴, are introduced.

Keywords: Networks, Neuroscience, Psychiatry, Graphs, Complexity, System

1. Conceptual Foundations of Network Neuroscience

1. Specific Technical Definitions: Systems, Networks/ Graphs (Table 1, Figure 1)

A fundamental understanding of systems and network theory, requires precise definitions of these terms (Table 1) and applied examples (Figure 2).

System	A precise definition of a real (not a conceptual) system, is: "A real system consists of parts interacting in space-time, exchanging material, energy, or information with each other and with the environment, creating physically measurable effects not attributable to actions of individual parts or to interactions of any proper subset of the parts. Real systems inhabit the material world and involve flows of material and energy. In addition to their material effects, these flows enable the creation and transmission of information in real systems" ¹⁷ .
Graph	Although the terms Graph and Network can be used interchangeably in the literature, there are specific technical definitions: A Graph is "the Abstract mathematical concept" describing, "artificial formations of nodes and edges" ¹⁸ . It is deliberately abstracted from selected sets of physical, functional, or logical relations.
Network	Is the graph representing a "real-world object" ¹⁸ "in which the nodes represent entities of the system and the edges represent the relationships among them" ¹⁸ .

Table 1. Detailed Technical Definitions of Systems, Graphs and Networks

Structural Foundations of the Mesolimbic Reward System: From Anatomy to Network

Figure 1. The mesolimbic system (PFC, VTA, NAcc, Amy, Hpc) and the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) regulating its rhythmic neurotransmitter expression, depicted as a real (brain) system, an abstract graph with edges and nodes and a network of functional interactions. Abbreviations: PFC: Prefrontal Cortex. NAcc: Nucleus Accumbens. VTA: Ventral Temporal Area. Amy: Amygdala. Hpc: Hippocampus. SCN: Suprachiasmatic Nucleus. Based on ¹⁹.

1.2. The concept of complexity

Network science developed through the study of complex natural and artificial systems ²⁰. It is grounded in the understanding that the complexity of a system arises, at the macroscopic or phenomenological level, from the way in which its structure combines elements of regularity and randomness, or regularity and irregularity ^{20, 21, 22, 23}.

More specifically, the complex behavior of a system is positively related to the existence of internal heterogeneity ²⁰. In this context, complexity increases when the elements of a system organize in patterns with various degrees of regularity; for example, connection and separation, ordered and less ordered patterns of association, linearity and nonlinearity, deterministic or non-deterministic interaction, feedback and adaptation.

At the same time, complex systems display emergent properties: properties that cannot be explained by the simple sum of the properties of their individual components, but instead arise, at least in part, through their self-organisation into a new and higher level of adaptation ^{21, 24}.

1.2.1 Complexity and emergent levels of organization in the human brain

In the human brain, the emergence ²⁵ of emotions, perception, memory, learning and consciousness, can be understood as the appearance of levels of organization through connections ²⁰ representing modular and/or synergistic interactions ²⁶; that is, through networks of relations. These relations extend across multiple biological and functional scales:

- Microscopic scale: genetic, biochemical, subcellular, cellular and intercellular levels;
- Mesoscopic scale: neuronal networks, cortical columns, cortical layers, subcortical structures, local signal-processing regions and large-scale networks of brain regions;
- Macroscopic phenomena: oscillatory activity, large-scale neural responses, adaptation and, ultimately, behaviour in relation to the external world.

Depending on the level of organization under study, node, edges and networks may represent different entities respectively. For example, at one level they may represent genes, gene–gene interactions and gene networks ²⁷. At another level they may represent neurons, neuronal interactions and neuronal networks ²⁷. At a higher behavioral or clinical level, they may represent symptoms, symptom–symptom statistical or conditional (and not necessarily causal) associations and symptom networks ²⁸.

Similarly, connections between neurons, cortical columns or brain regions may be structural or functional. Structural connectivity provides the anatomical substrate of functional connectivity and therefore constrains (but does not fully determine) the possible combinations of functional interactions among the elements of a given level of brain organization.

1.2.2. Complexity and heterogeneity in the human brain (Figure 2)

The organization of the human brain is not random, but the result of a complicated evolutionary process. The human connectivity network (or connectome) contains organized features of both high regularity and sparse long-range connectivity. High regularity is reflected in dense connections between anatomically and functionally related regions; sparse long-range connections link distant brain areas in a selective manner²². This architecture allows the brain to combine functional segregation and functional integration²³. Segregation refers to the relative functional specialization and independence of distinct modules (including cell clusters, neural columns, regions and areas) in the brain, whereas integration refers to the capacity of distributed modules to interact and coordinate information processing and transfer.

This organization is closely related to the small-world property, a characteristic of many complex networks in nature, which supports efficient communication by combining:

- neighborhoods) compared with random networks and
- short mean path lengths²⁰ (short average minimum number of edges from a node N_x to a node N_y in a network of points and connections)²⁰, compared to regular lattices. The term “random” in this context does not imply random brain organization but the mathematical similarity of the specific “random” configuration with a random distribution of connections²⁹.

As the relation between efficiency and path length is inverse²⁰, this specific type of brain organization is particularly important because both i. the execution of established functional routines and ii. the adaptation to novel conditions in the brain, require parallel processing and increased functional efficiency in different parts at the same time, as well as rapid integration of the processed stimuli across distributed brain systems.

Figure 2. Representation of the layered organization of the brain and the main concepts of i. emergence in different scales (Left) and ii. heterogeneity leading to a hybrid pattern of connectivity, combining segregation and integration (Right).

2. Network theory: from heterogeneity to emergent properties

2.1. General principles

Aim of network theory is to describe, the organization of a heterogeneous complex system ²⁰. Individual elements of the system, such as neurons or brain regions, are represented as vertices or nodes, numbered from 1 to N. Relations among these elements (for example the transfer of information between functionally related areas during a psychometric task) are represented as edges, which may range from absent to numerous, and may be directed or undirected, binary or weighted.

In this way, a network can be represented spatially, for example in two or three dimensions. Such a representation allows the investigator to describe the global organization of a network and some of its properties ³¹: how the elements of the network are connected, how they organize into groups, and how individual elements or groups may remain partially independent or partially insulated within the broader network ^{30,31}.

2.2. Identification and measurement of network properties

2.2.1. Identification of a network (Fig.3, 1-4, SI-Tab.1)

The first step in the application of network theory is the identification (delineation) of a network, in relation to the relevant research question, within a larger set of elements ^{4,28,31,32,33}. In some systems, the remaining elements may participate in other networks; in others, they may not participate in any clearly defined network. The network of interest may therefore appear as a specific form of self-organization within a broader environment. Once the network has been identified, the next steps are its spatial representation, the calculation of graph-theoretical metrics and, finally, the interpretation of these results in relation to the function of the system ³¹.

In brain research, the identification of a network is usually performed through a recording or imaging method selected according to a specific research question. (for example: “which areas of the brain are active during the working memory task X” where fMRI can be used). The main methods used in practice for this purpose include electroencephalography, magnetoencephalography, structural MRI, functional MRI and diffusion MRI, including diffusion tensor imaging (DTI). The participant may be studied during sleep, rest, task performance, psychometric assessment or another experimentally defined condition. In the case of structural MRI, the measurement is not directly dependent on the (immediate) behavioural state of the participant, although structural measurements may still be related to clinical, developmental or experimental variables ³⁴ (Figure 3.1).

For the human brain, network identification is a special case of a broader problem: the extraction of an embedded network from a broader, already interconnected biological system. The brain is not a collection of isolated elements. Rather, all regions in the brain are, to some degree, structurally or functionally related to other regions ³⁵. Thus, brain network analysis does not

usually discover a network in an otherwise empty space; it estimates a specific pattern of relations within a wider, highly interconnected system.

In practice, after acquisition, the data are processed using specialized software (for example FreeSurfer for sMRI, fMRI or DTI data, MATLAB for EEG) in order to

- Clear noise signals from predefined areas of interest (ROIs, used as nodes of the network/graph) on a brain map and/ (Figure 3.2 and 3.3)
- identify statistically or structurally meaningful associations, used as edges of the network/graph, among areas of the brain (predefined ROIs or not) (Figure 3.4).
- extract measurements from the areas of interest

The type of nodes and connections (edges) depends on the modality and the research question^{31,36,37,38,39}. In functional MRI, EEG or MEG, an edge may represent different measures of functional association between signals (temporal correlation, coherence, phase synchrony, directed influence). In diffusion MRI, an edge may represent estimated anatomical connectivity or tract strength. In structural MRI, especially in group-level analyses, an edge may represent covariance or correlation between cortical thickness, cortical volume or surface area between regions across individuals. At a higher behavioural or clinical level, networks may also be constructed from symptoms. In this case, nodes represent symptoms⁴⁰ and edges represent statistical associations, conditional dependencies or other estimated relations between symptoms in large samples of healthy individuals or patients.

2.2.2. Construction of the connectivity matrix and measurement of network metrics (Fig.3, 5-8)

Once the research question has been formulated³¹ and a network has been defined, its organization can be studied quantitatively.

Figure 3. Basic steps of brain network identification and analysis.

The adjacency matrix provides the basis for the calculation of network metrics and the subsequent research on their relevant properties. Characteristic examples are ^{4,28}:

- The degree to which specific nodes are connected to other nodes (important metric: degree centrality);
- The degree of clustering among groups of already connected elements (important metric: clustering coefficient);
- The extent to which the network is organized into subsets: communities or relatively independent nodes (important metric: modularity)
- The topological distance between connected groups, which is particularly important when the movement of information, signals or influence through the system occurs over time (metric: path length, characteristic path length); Topological distance can be broadly defined as the measure of how far two points are in the network, based on the steps (connections) between them rather than their physical distance ³⁰.
- The extent to which connections appear randomly, systematically or according to specific organizational principles within and between groups (important metrics: Small-worldness, randomness, regularity, assortativity, rich-club organization, motif structure, degree distribution); ²⁰.

Other commonly used metrics include, strength, global efficiency, betweenness centrality, eigenvector centrality, participation coefficient and rich-club organization. Definitions for these metrics, are presented in Figures 4 and 5. More detailed definitions and mathematical descriptions can be found in ^{20,28,29,42,43,44} and a short Glossary at ^{45,46}.

Figure 4. Core network measures used in graph/ network analysis.

Additional Important Network Measures

Useful metrics beyond those listed in the text

Other important metrics often used in brain and network analysis include: strength, closeness centrality, eigenvector centrality/PageRank, local efficiency, participation coefficient, within-module degree z-score, rich-club coefficient, small-worldness, reciprocity, k-core / core-periphery, edge betweenness, and algebraic connectivity.

These measures are complementary; the most informative choice depends on whether the network is **structural** or **functional**, **weighted** or **binary**, **directed** or **undirected**, **static** or **dynamic**.

Figure 5. Additional metrics extracted from graph/ network analysis.

Interpretation of network metrics

Network metrics derived from the $N \times N$ multivariate adjacency matrix (full table at ^{47-Append.A}) should not be chosen and interpreted mechanically: Metric selection and translation to biological and clinical meaning, are context-related and dependent on multiple parameters (including biological

or clinical question under investigation, type of data, definition of nodes and edges, preprocessing pipeline/ artifact control, threshold, connectivity density, network size) (SI-Fig,1)^{4,28,31,47,48,49}. After careful formulation of the primary research questions³¹, parameter selection and consideration of parameter limitations (SI-Tab.2), analysis results can be used for:

The suggestion of structural, functional, transcriptomic and other types of networks underlying healthy and patient brain function in different contexts of age, sex and social environment²⁸. A case study of selective application of network metrics and their interpretation is presented in Figure 6, based on⁵².

Generation of hypotheses on causal mechanisms connecting and regulating networks of different elements and different layers of organization of healthy or patient brain function^{28,48,50}.

Comparison a. between networks and b. between the changes inside networks derived from samples of healthy controls and patient groups, for the discovery of candidate diagnostic or prognostic biomarkers^{1,2,3,28,31}. As an example, expanding the research protocol of the case study⁵⁰ to a larger sample of patients with depression and controls, could allow for the machine-learning supported generation of a characteristic biosignature, based on connectivity strength differences between patients and controls in the mesolimbic reward system, for the classification between patients and controls.

SELECTIVE APPLICATION OF NETWORK METRICS IN NEUROSCIENCE

Example: Functional connectivity of the mesolimbic reward system

Abbreviations: ROI = region of interest; rs-fMRI = resting-state functional MRI; FC = functional connectivity; VTA = ventral tegmental area; NAcc = nucleus accumbens; PFC = prefrontal cortex; Amy = amygdala; Hpc = hippocampus; SCN = suprachiasmatic nucleus.

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